

PPGPPMET.PWY..ppGpp.metabolism

15000
10000
5000
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

PWY.4984..urea.cycle

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

PWY.5189..tetrapyrrole.biosynthesis.II..from.glycine.

PWY.6936..seleno.amino.acid.biosynthesis..plants.

75000
50000
25000
0

0 100 200 300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

